

THE DISCUSSION ON FACADES' SOUND INSULATION IN SLOVAKIA

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Abstract:

Standard energy retrofitting of buildings in Slovakia has over the last decades led to an increase of thermal insulation of the building envelope. In order to provide more benefits to building users, considering also other, non-energetic aspects, an increased interest can be seen on the improvement of indoor acoustic comfort.

Our everyday experience shows, that when it comes to the assessment of the quality of building façades, many shortcomings can be seen in the design, realisation and even in legislation. Decisions on criteria and requirements in building acoustics and thus also on requirements on the building envelope, are based on the recommendation of World Health Organisation that uses large scale studies on noise effects on health. Standards typically suggest minimum sound insulation properties of the building elements for exposure to exterior noise.

The most typical examples of the standard energy retrofitting of buildings in Slovakia, involve dwelling houses (usually massive façades with External Thermal Insulation Composite System ETICS), administrative buildings (light-weight façades – single leaf or double leaf) and industrial buildings (insulation of noise generated inside buildings).

This contribution is listing the weak points and crucial parts of façades' design, typical for Slovak architecture.

Key words: sound insulation, façades, building acoustics

1. INTRODUCTION

The main function of partition constructions, especially façades, is to protect the building users (inhabitants, employees etc). The usual goal is to achieve thermal, light, humidity and acoustic comfort in the interior's buildings (in other words to fulfil hygienic requirements). In case of industrial buildings, we are often designing façades to protect also the external environment against a sound propagation from noise generated by machines located inside industrial objects. Nowadays, it is relatively easy to get all the important information on façades sound insulation requirements from national legislation and standards [1].

Target requirements are closely related to the maximum acceptable noise level values in the environment (interior and exterior as well). All criteria are slightly following the recommendations of the World Health Organization

(WHO). WHO recommends acceptable maximum noise levels in relation to the human activity [2,3]. Partition structures' sound insulation requirements, their Qualitative evaluation and the way of measurement partially differs depending on country [4].

In Slovakia, depending on the building technology development and cultural and society changes we are dealing with, a diverse spectrum of façade constructions exists. Whether dealing with historic or modern façades, they can be divided as lightweight or massive façades, single or multilayer (two or more layers), ventilated or unventilated, mounted, sandwich, brick or monolithic façades.

Each façade type has its own specifics and justification within the design. Façades' system complexity makes the system less predictable from building acoustics point of view, whether due to resonances in the façade and its

elements, as well as the way of its anchoring and acoustic details design solutions.

In this paper, we will present an overview of the most common façade systems in Slovakia and address their acoustic weaknesses.

Gradually, we will present the influence of external thermal insulation composite system (ETICS) on the decrease of sound insulation of massive façades, we will outline the issue of transparent lightweight cladding, especially of transparent single layer façades and double transparent naturally ventilated façades.

1. EXTERNAL THERMAL INSULATION COMPOSITE SYSTEMS (ETICS)

In connection with the global trend of energy savings, in Slovakia we are adding thermal insulation on façades since eighties of 20th century. After years, the thermal insulation thickness gradually increased from 40mm up to 200 to 300mm on new façades at present times. Although thermal insulation significantly improves the enveloping constructions thermal insulation properties and reduces the buildings' energy needs, in specific cases it reduces the sound insulation of the structures. In Slovakia, the most widely used thermal insulation systems are the external thermal insulation composite systems (ETICS), where the thermal insulation layer is made of polystyrene, mineral wool or glass wool. Thermally insulated wall behaves as a mass spring system, where the thermal insulation (e.g. Mineral Wool) acts as a spring in the system.

Nowadays, we are able to predict at what frequency the ETICS will resonate [5-12]. Publication [8] showed that, the influence on the sound insulation due to ETICS can vary from -8dB to +19dB. Current practice, based on extensive research of Weber et al. [6], is to predict the influence of ETICS on façades sound insulation by means of the relationships given in the standard ISO 12354-1.

Another prediction model to estimate the effect on the sound reduction improvement index ΔR was given by Urban et al. [14] (Eq. 1).

$$\Delta R_{f_0 < f < f_c} = 20 \log \left(m \frac{f}{\rho_0 \cdot c} \right) + 10 \log \left(\frac{f}{f_c} - 1 \right) + 10 \log(\eta) \quad (1)$$

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where η is the structural loss factor of the wall without ETICS, m is the mass of plaster ρ_0 is the density of air, f denotes the frequency (Hz) and f_c is the theoretical coincidence frequency of the plaster layer of the ETICS. Santoni et al. [15] developed a model that takes the influence of anchors, as commonly used in ETICS, into account. Furthermore, Urban et al. studied a theoretical relation of thermal insulation material choice influence on

the resulting sound insulation spectra [16]. In this study eight different material types were chosen, split up into three groups (see **Table 1.**).

Variable	Mineral Wool	Rigid Foam	EPS
$\rho(\text{kg/m}^3)$	53,1 to 112,8	35,8	13,6 to 14,8
d (m)	0,13 to 0,15	0,08	0,11 to 0,15
s (MN/m ³)	4,4 to 10,6	57,7	33,0 to 42,0
ΔR (dB)	2 to 11	-6	-4 to -3
ΔC (dB)	-1 to -9	-4	-4 to -3
ΔC_{tr} (dB)	-4 to -14	-4	-5 to -4

Table 1. Theoretical influence of ETICS on the sound reduction improvement index.

2. LIGHTWEIGHT TRANSPARENT FACADES

The most widely used façades used for administrative buildings are lightweight cladding, specially based on a combination of glass and aluminium. They allow architects to create large transparent surfaces with variable dimensions and shapes.

2.1. Single leaf façades

Single layer façades are the most common transparent type of façades. Thanks to the development in building constructions, today we can design façades having a high sound insulation as well as a high thermal insulation. By improving the façades of the transparent parts (glassing), the weakness of façades became the aluminium parts, the details of the joints and the anchoring of the façades [17]. These parts are in many cases spreading sound energy in the construction. Finding the best solution for façades, the construction of the joints of their parts and the design of the inner walls connection while keeping the lowest possible cost becomes an important issue. The problem is the mass of the given type of façades, where the coincidence frequency and the natural resonance frequencies are both in the sound insulation spectrum, while in case of massive walls the structural resonance is usually below 100Hz. Because of this, a massive wall most oftenly has a better R_w . Other problems can be caused by structural-acoustic resonances of hollow aluminium mullions, which are commonly used on in façades constructions [18]. Despite the fact that the area of the mullions is only a fraction of the façade surface in

comparison to the glazing parts, its deteriorating influence on façade acoustic properties can be significant. Major complications may also cause an inappropriate solution to the dilation between façade panels.

2. 2. Double transparent naturally ventilated façades

Other type of lightweight façades are double skin naturally ventilated façades (DTF). DTF's were initially designed to improve the thermal insulation properties of façades and to reduce the energy requirements of buildings. Subsequently, they were also being applied to design objects in urban areas with high noise exposure. In this case the exterior layer of façade works as a "buffer or shield". In Slovakia, commonly used DTF types are naturally ventilated with a width of façade cavity between 0.15 and 1.5m. This allows the user to ventilate the façades cavity, which increases their comfort. In general, the positive effect of the outer DTF layer on the sound insulation is about $\Delta R \approx 6$ dB in comparison to a single leaf façade. Significant research in this area has been published in [19], where the author's goal was to supplement the standard EN 12354-3 [20] by a prediction model applicable to a DTF.

An empirical model was published in [21], which is based on insitu and laboratory measurement data. The authors distinguish two ways of ventilation (slit or mesh), and divided the frequency spectrum into three regions:

- The frequency range with sound insulation behaviour dominated by transmission enhancement due to cavity resonances (Eq.2).
- The frequency range with sound insulation behaviour dominated by the transmission of sound via the ventilation slots (Eq.3).
- The frequency range above the coincidence frequency of the external wall (Eq.4).

$$R_{f \leq f_0} = R_1 + R_2 - 4 \text{ dB} \quad (2)$$

$$R_{f_0 \rightarrow f_{cr}} = R_{f_0} + 6 \text{ or } 9 \text{ dB/oct} \quad (3)$$

$$R_{f_{cr} \rightarrow f} = R_{max} + 6 \text{ dB} \quad (4)$$

From an acoustic point of view, the standing waves occurring in the façade cavity often constitute the biggest problem. Standing wave resonance, ventilation elements and other resonances (critical and natural) often cause acoustic problems both for single leaf façades and for DTF's. Furthermore, the anchoring, joints and interior construction connection to the façades are very often causing acoustic bridges in the system.

3. CONCLUSION

This article presents an overview of the current issues of façades and their acoustic properties in Slovakia. It presents an overview of various approaches to predicting the acoustic performance of External Thermal Insulation Composite Systems (ETICS). The mass spring mass resonance generated by interaction of the plaster and the thermal insulation layer are the determining parameters that need to be considered during façades' design. It also recalls the issue of lightweight cladding. It points to their weak spots such as hollow aluminium mullions, aluminium frames, anchoring solutions and joints between façade and interior structures. Also DTFs, despite the indisputably better acoustic properties than simple façades, have their weak spots as a solution of the ventilation elements and the standing waves occurring in the façade cavity. The field that was addressed in this article is wind induced sounds. This phenomenon is becoming more and more important due to the construction of high-rise buildings with high airflow rates. In all these areas, extensive research is under way in Europe with the aim of designing better façade solutions.

3. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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